

Activity-oriented Project Governance (APGov) Framework Components

S/No.	Component	Description
1.	Subject	The individual or group that is undertaking the project governance activity (e.g., middle manager, senior management, developer, agile project team). Analysis of the project governance activity is informed by the subject's viewpoint.
2.	Object	The problem, situation, or focus of the project governance activity (e.g., governing and completing agile software development project). It is an objectified motive: the thing being acted upon.
3.	Rules and norms	Regulations, norms, conventions (explicit and implicit) that constrain/govern the project governance activity. These may include project governance rules, policies, principles, procedures, processes, methods (e.g., agile methods), standard practices that the subject is expected to follow or comply with when acting on the object.

S/No.	Component	Description
4.	Community of significant others	Individuals or groups other than the subject who have the same general object, but are distinct, and with whom subject interacts i.e. other stakeholders. This includes other internal and external actors associated with the project governance activity.
5.	Division of labour	Represents the roles, responsibilities, and hierarchy of various actors in the project governance activity and indicates the way tasks are divided.
6.	Tools	A thing used by the subject (or members of community of significant others) to act on the object in order to achieve the outcome. Tools can be physical (material) or abstract (non-material) project governance tools. Examples of physical project governance tools include agile methods' artifacts (e.g., Kanban board, burn-down charts), workplace software applications, technologies, documented policies and procedures, and various project related documentation. Examples of abstract project governance tools include job-specific competences, models, frameworks, product vision, project goals, and team goals.
	Job-specific competences tools – Input competences	Represents the knowledge, skills, understanding, abilities, expertise, and experience of the subject (or members of community of significant others), which they bring to their job in order to perform it in the project governance activity. It refers to abilities and capabilities possessed by the subject (or members of community of significant others) as a result of experience, qualifications, education or training, which enables them to do their job in the project governance activity.
	Job-specific competences tools – Output competences	The way the subject (or members of community of significant others) demonstrates knowledge, skills, understanding, abilities, expertise, and experience when performing their job in the project governance activity. This entails the manner by which the subject (or members of community of significant others) shows that they can do the job. It is the demonstration of abilities and capabilities by the subject (or members of community of significant others) in performing their job to acceptable levels of job performance in the project governance activity.
	Job-specific competences tools – Personal competences	The personal attributes, character, personality of the subject (or members of community of significant others), which they bring to the job in order to perform it in the project governance activity. The personality characteristics that enables the subject (or members of community of significant others) to do their job in the project governance activity.
7.	Outcome	The outcome (expected results) of the project governance activity, which is the transformed object (e.g., a governed and completed agile software development project that meets business targets and achieves senior management objectives).
8.	Motivation	The reason(s) for the project governance activity taking place. Activities can be poly-motivational, implying that motivations behind activities can vary. Activity actors may have different motives, which can also lead to contradictions. Motives are linked to a person or group's need.
9.	Action	A conscious goal-driven deed or effort targeted at and performed upon the object by the subject in order to achieve an outcome in the project governance activity (e.g., monitoring action, coordination action, goal setting action).

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10.	Operation	An unconscious, routinised or automatic deed (or occurrence), which is targeted at and performed upon the object by the subject in order to achieve an outcome in the project governance activity. For example, operations related to monitoring or coordination.